

Effect of seedling age at transplanting on establishment, maturity, grain yield, and straw-grain ratio of 3 rice varieties, 1977-78 kharif, Allahabad, India.^a

Age of seedlings (days)	Establishment (DT)			Time between PE & maturity (days)			Maturity (days)			Grain yield (t/ha)			Straw-grain ratio		
	B	R	S	B	R	S	B	R	S	B	R	S	B	R	S
25	6	6	6	35	48	50	109	128	130	2.7	2.6	2.4	1.18	1.26	1.19
35	5	5	5	30	45	35	117	130	132	2.0	2.8	2.8	1.31	1.30	1.42
45	5	5	5	28	40	37	120	133	135	2.0	1.9	2.1	1.26	1.26	1.37
55	5	4	4	22	30	31	131	135	141	0.8	0.8	1.3	1.21	1.19	1.21

^aDT = days after transplanting. B = Bala. R = Ratna. S = Sona. PE = panicle emergence. Grain yield: highly significant for seedling-age treatment. LSD for seedling-age treatments: 0.381. LSD for variety treatments: 0.258.

that were older at planting. In contrast, seedlings that were transplanted at an older age matured later. That could account for the greater setback at different growth stages of older seedlings. Relatively older seedlings of Ratna and Sona gave the highest grain yields when transplanted at 35 days but gave lower

yields when transplanted later. The straw-grain ratio, which was highest in 35-day-old seedlings, decreased in older seedlings, which grew and developed poorly.

It may be concluded that rice seedlings should be transplanted in alkali soils between the ages of 25 and 35 days. If

transplanted earlier, the seedlings may die; if transplanted later, they will yield poorly. The finding could be due to the higher concentration of soluble salts that results in the higher mortality of seedlings planted when between 21 and 25 days old. Thus, the older seedlings do better in saline alkali soils. ■

Potassium chloride pretreatment on rice seeds

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A field trial was conducted to determine the efficiency and response of rice seedlings to nutrients available in the soil. The variety ADT31 was used in a two-replication split-plot design.

The main plot treatments were M1 -- green leaf manure at 5 t/ha; M2 -- M1 + superphosphate at 250 kg/ha; M3 -- M2 + blue-green algae at 25 kg/ha; M4 -- nitrogen placed at 75 kg N/ha; and M5 -- control (no manure).

The subplot treatments were S1 --

Grain yield of fertilized rice plants and pretreated rice seeds. Tamil Nadu, India.

Main plot	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) over control	Subplot	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) over control
M1	3.6	116	S1	3.1	100
M2	3.7	120	S2	4.2	135
M3	3.5	114	S3	3.8	121
M4	4.2	134	S4	3.6	115
M5	3.1	100	S5	3.3	106
			S6	3.7	119
<i>'F' test</i>					
SE	122.0			45.1	
LSD	0.480			0.131	

control; S2 -- potassium chloride 1% (seed soaking); S3 -- manganese sulfate 8% (seed soaking); S4 -- ferrous sulfate 8% (seed soaking); S5 -- diammonium phosphate 4% (sprouted seed treatment); and S6 -- zinc sulfate 4% (sprouted seed treatment).

Among the main plot treatments, M4 gave a 34% higher yield than the control (see table).

Among the subplot treatments, S2 was significantly superior treatments and gave the highest grain yield, 35.0% over the control. ■

Rice-based cropping systems

Performance of improved agricultural practices for dryland rice production in Sierra Leone

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Trials were conducted for the past 3 years on rice in farmers' fields under

dryland ecology at sites across Sierra Leone to determine:

1. If permanent cultivation can replace the bush fallow-rice system of traditional cultivation.
2. If improved cultivation methods can increase the yields of traditional rice varieties.
3. The benefit-cost ratio due to

fertilizer application.

Upland farmers in this part of Africa every year clear the bush from a new site and abandon that site after one rice crop or a crop of groundnut, cassava, or both, and return to the same site 8-10 years later. The fallow period has been reduced to 4-5 years in some parts of Sierra Leone.